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Update of Report on dissemination and communication activities 1

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Document History

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V0.2	Jul 7, 2025	Input in section 2
V0.3	Jul 13, 2025	Contribution to Annexes
V0.4	Oct 03, 2025	Input in sections 1 and 3; check of formatting
V1.0	Oct 10, 2025	Final version for submission

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Definitions

The definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [[ref](#)].

List of Abbreviations

EAB	Ethics Advisory Board
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
PDEC	Plan for dissemination, exploration, and communication activities
SAB	Sustainability Advisory Board
SULO	Simplified Upper-Level Ontology
VA	Virtual Assistant

Executive Summary

The report examines the results of the planned activities under D6.2 “Plan for Dissemination & exploitation of Results incl. Communication Activities (PDEC)” and D6.8 “Update of the PDEC in official report 1”. Deliverable D6.10 is the follow-up update on deliverable D6.7 “Report on dissemination and communication activities” and provides more information about the activities planned to be performed over the past 18 months for the period M19-M36.

This document presents a detailed report reviewing all activities related to dissemination, including scientific publications, participation in conferences, presentations at scientific events, and networking with scientific communities. The communication report includes a formal assessment of the project's visibility and social networking activities related to it. All these activities are carried out as part of WP6 “Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Sustainability” in the AIDAVA project. Our key achievements illustrated with numbers are as follows:

- Communication tools: project website that is regularly updated (**28,640 visitors**, with an average of **29.60** minutes per session and **71.38** page impressions), audio-visual materials, and six-monthly periodic flash in 3 languages (mostly targeted at patients).
- Publications: Total number of **peer-reviewed publications** is **20** and the total number of **preprints** is **8**, which received 735 citations in Google Scholar. 15 of these papers were indexed in Scopus and 10 publications indexed in PubMed Central. We have achieved an **h-index of 6** in Google Scholar with 735 citations, Scopus with 378 citations, and Web of Science with 296 citations, excluding self-citations.
- AIDAVA **public deliverables** published in Zenodo accumulated **1,780 views**, 1,385 downloads, which gives an average of 84.76 views per deliverable and 65.95 downloads.
- AIDAVA project results were presented in **8 events**, including scientific conferences and workshops.

All further dissemination and communication activities will be reported in D6.11 Update of Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities 2 (due M48).

1. Introduction

AIDAVA's innovative approach, combining AI-powered tools with a patient-centric model, shapes and drives the project's communication, dissemination, and networking efforts as well. We are committed to empowering patients by giving them insight and control over their health data, which in itself is transformed into a high-quality reusable resource. This is also how the consortium handles its outreach objectives: to communicate about results clearly and transparently, to give back (practical tooling and research advances) to the scientific and patient communities, who support us along the way.

In the second phase of the project, we have been leveraging and building upon the good foundation laid in the first 18 months through the recognizable branding, communication channels, and dissemination framework that encourages open access and public sharing. Stakeholder engagement has become an even more crucial part of our strategy in order to inform and facilitate the technical enhancement of the AIDAVA virtual assistant.

Our collaborative achievements are described in detail in this document. Beyond the introductory part, Section 2 elaborates on the activities performed by the consortium in the period M19-M36. It contains three subsections: the first one provides an update on the developments around multipurpose tools and materials; the second reports on dissemination activities, including scientific publications, participation in scientific and clustering events; and the last part presents the project's communication outreach through digital and physical platforms. Section 3 includes a conclusion. Finally, Appendix 1 provides an up-to-date list of project publications, and Appendix 2 exemplifies some of the consortium's communication and dissemination activities.

2. Description of Activities

2.1. Multipurpose tools and materials

The multipurpose tools and materials play a crucial role in reaching broader audiences and providing up-to-date information about the AIDAVA project results, activities, and objectives. Such tools are the project website, internal AIDAVA platform, audio-video materials, AIDAVA toolkit, and printed materials like tote bags, pens, notebooks, among others. The AIDAVA communication toolkit (see deliverable D6.4 “AIDAVA communication toolkit”³) was designed by EURICE at the beginning of the project and aims to foster project visibility and recognition.

The developed physical promotional materials for the AIDAVA project – pens, tote bags, notebooks – were distributed during the scientific and networking events to promote the project and provide visibility.

From the broader search in the world wide web, the search results prove that all results related to the AIDAVA project in the two widely used search engines – Google and Microsoft Bing (see Figure 1 and Figure 2), as well as the AIDAVA brand colour code, logo, and all communication and dissemination materials – these are easily recognizable as related to the AIDAVA project. In addition, all top search results are only related to AIDAVA project activities, which demonstrates high visibility of the project.

Figure 1 Search results for "AIDAVA project" in Google - images and all

Figure 2 Search results in Microsoft Bing - images and all

³ D6.4 “AIDAVA communication toolkit” <https://zenodo.org/records/15434311>

2.1.1. Project website

The AIDAVA project website⁴ was developed by EURICE during the first reporting period M1-M18. Detailed description of the website organisation and structure is available in the deliverable D6.1 “Public project website”⁵. The content of the AIDAVA website is regularly updated with news, events, interviews, AIDAVA events, project results, and periodic flash. For the period M19-M36, 25 new entries were added to the website in the section “News & Events” (Figure 3). The difference between “Event” and “AIDAVA events” is that the first one comprises all related events to the AIDAVA project, and the former one is focused on events organised by AIDAVA. Some highlights from this rubric are presented on Figure 4. The AIDAVA website gained a lot of attention during the period, accumulating in total of:

- **28,640 visitors** – the number of distinct individuals or devices that visit the AIDAVA website within a given period;
- with an average of **29.60 minutes per session** – a single period of user interaction with the AIDAVA website;
- **71.38 page impressions** – the total count of times any web page on the AIDAVA website is viewed or loaded by a user.

These statistics indicate that AIDAVA project developments and results have sparked interest, as website visitors tend not only to browse through the pages on a single occasion but return to check the recent updates and follow the progress of AIDAVA.

Figure 3 AIDAVA website “News & Events” section updates

⁴ <https://aidava.eu/>

⁵ D6.1 “Public project website” <https://zenodo.org/records/15433862>

The screenshot shows the 'News' section of the AIDAVA website. It features a navigation bar with categories: SHOW ALL, AIDAVA EVENTS, CONFERENCES, EVENTS, INTERVIEWS, NEWS, OPINION PAPER, and PERIODIC FLASH. The main content area displays a list of news items, each with a date, a title, a brief description, and a 'READ MORE' button. The items include:

- 08/07/2025**: **AIDAVA at HIMSS Europe: Personalised Data, Quality and the Future of Health Systems**. From 10-12 June 2025, HIMSS Europe brought together leading figures in the fields of digital health and data-driven innovation in Paris. AIDAVA was proud to be represented by our clinical coordinator. [READ MORE](#)
- 25/06/2025**: **Save the Date: i-HD Annual Conference 2025, 3-4 December 2025 and AIDAVA hackathon on 2nd December 2025**. Our AIDAVA partner, the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i-HD) invites all health data enthusiasts to its Annual Conference 2025: 'A Decade of Joining the Dots - Towards Bridg'. [READ MORE](#)
- 19/06/2025**: **European Heart Network (EHN) Annual Workshop and General Assembly in Stockholm, Sweden**. Last week AIDAVA partner European Heart Network (EHN) hosted its Annual Workshop and General Assembly in Stockholm. Kristof Vanfraechem, Founder and CEO, Data for Patients introduced the AIDAVA a... [READ MORE](#)
- 01/04/2025**: **AIDAVA featured in a recent Healthcare IT News article**. AIDAVA's innovative approach to personal health data curation is featured in a recent Healthcare IT News article. The piece explores how AIDAVA leverages AI-driven solutions to enable individuals to e... [READ MORE](#)
- 08/07/2025**: **AIDAVA at HIMSS Europe: Personalised Data, Quality and the Future of Health Systems**. From 10-12 June 2025, HIMSS Europe brought together leading figures in the fields of digital health and data-driven innovation in Paris. AIDAVA was proud to be represented by our clinical coordinator. [READ MORE](#)
- 25/06/2025**: **Save the Date: i-HD Annual Conference 2025, 3-4 December 2025 and AIDAVA hackathon on 2nd December 2025**. Our AIDAVA partner, the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i-HD) invites all health data enthusiasts to its Annual Conference 2025: 'A Decade of Joining the Dots - Towards Bridg'. [READ MORE](#)
- 19/06/2025**: **European Heart Network (EHN) Annual Workshop and General Assembly in Stockholm, Sweden**. Last week AIDAVA partner European Heart Network (EHN) hosted its Annual Workshop and General Assembly in Stockholm. Kristof Vanfraechem, Founder and CEO, Data for Patients introduced the AIDAVA a... [READ MORE](#)
- 01/04/2025**: **AIDAVA at HIMSS Europe in Paris from 10-12 June**. Our clinical coordinator Isabelle de Zegher will be at HIMSS Europe in Paris from 10-12 June, presenting the progress of the AIDAVA project and the initial results. With interactive formats and expert... [READ MORE](#)
- 06/03/2025**: **AIDAVA at SWAT4HCLS 2025**. Our partners Shervin Mehryar and Renshi Celsbi from the Institute of Data Science at Maastricht University attended 'SWAT4HCLS 2025: Bridging Life Sciences and Technology' from 24-27 February 2025 in B... [READ MORE](#)

Figure 4 Highlights from the News & Events section from the AIDAVA website in the period M19-M36

In addition, the AIDAVA project results section is periodically updated, containing a comprehensive list of scientific publications and deliverables. More information about them is available in Section 2.2 and Appendix 1 List of publications.

Another updated section on the AIDAVA website is the information about the Ethics Advisory Board and Sustainability Advisory Board, including names and links to LinkedIn profiles of all experts (Figure 5 and Figure 6 Ethics Advisory Board section on the AIDAVA website Figure 6). This allows transparency of the Advisory Board members for external website visitors and demonstrates that the AIDAVA project follows recommendations of highly reputable and knowledgeable experts in the area.

Sustainability Advisory Board (SAB)

AIDAVA has involved an external Sustainability Advisory Board (SAB) who will pave the way for sustainable uptake of results.

Mission

The Sustainability Advisory Board's mission is to oversee the Exploitation and Dissemination Activities of the project (WP6) and provide feedback during regular meetings on innovation, market needs, and economic potential of KERs and promote integration of the AIDAVA results. More specifically the SAB is expected to oversee the results of two key workshops: Exploitation & Sustainability Strategy Workshop and Exploitation & Sustainability Planning Workshop during which the project will validate the Key Exploitable Result (KER) candidates, revise, and refine associated exploitation strategies, and to develop concrete action plans via an Exploitation Roadmap.

Composition & Operations

The SAB will include ten opinion leaders/C-level executives from hospitals, public health authorities, EMA, pharma and EHR vendors and by the senior executives from the consortium partners. Consortium partners will nominate their representatives during the first General Assembly and will propose candidate participants for the board. Candidates will be elected on a majority voting system and invited by the chair of the board, Mr Agris Peedu (CEO of [NEMC](#)).

The SAB will meet every six months: once a year through teleconference (½ day meeting), once a year joining the life General Assembly (full day meeting). The project is expected to last for four years. Before each meeting, SAB members will be provided with an update of the project and a set of key topics to discuss and relevant documentation, in support of the topics. The advice by the SAB will be reported in official deliverables of the project. Meetings and reporting will be supported by Partner [NEMC](#) acting as secretariat of the SAB.

Members

<p>Clayton Hamilton WHO Regional Office for Europe's Division for Country Health Policies and Systems</p> <p>in LINKEDIN</p>	<p>Faisal Khan NovoNordisk</p> <p>in LINKEDIN</p>	<p>Dmitry Etin Independent Consultant/Deggendorf Institute of Technology</p> <p>in LINKEDIN</p>
<p>Michael Strübin EHTEL</p>	<p>Petr Holub BBMRI-ERIC</p>	<p>Markus Kalliola Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra</p>

Figure 5 Sustainability Advisory Board section on the AIDAVA website

Ethics Advisory Board (EAB)

AIDAVA is fortunate to have an independent Ethics Advisory Board of Experts (EAB). Its role is to provide an additional oversight for the project to consider ethics and data protection matters. The role supports the existing legal and ethical work of each of the partners, who have their own legal teams and research ethics committees overseeing their activities in the project.

The EAB is chaired by Don Willison from University of Toronto. He is joined by Julie Power, Patient Founder and Patient Support at Vasculitis Ireland Awareness, Brendan Barnes, former Privacy Officer at EFPIA, and Peter Singleton, an independent Information Governance Expert and Director of Cambridge Health Informatics.

Key contributions

Key contributions from the EAB have been providing advice on several topics, based on their extensive prior experience across several different projects and Health Information Technology developments.

- › How best to present the AIDAVA's work to local Research Ethics Committees
- › Data access and management advice to protect patients' privacy interests
- › Supporting the exploration and understanding of legal and ethical issues, focusing on the impacts these may have for participants and their care teams, and what they mean for the project goals.
- › How to better identify and respond to patients' overall interests across the project – to complement the Patient Advisory Group
- › Suggestions on how best to meet Data Protection regulatory requirements (including GDPR) and other data governance needs
- › Ensuring that communications to patients are clear and provide realistic expectations regarding project benefits
- › How best to capture wider learnings from the data handling processes, to inform future research.
- › Sharing reflections on what the project experience teaches us about scale-up and accessibility to the wider patient community.

EAB activities carried out so far

- › The EAB have had a hands-on approach to understanding the project. They have participated in a pilot workshop, working with our patient consultants to enhance the studies using G1 for understanding patient experience.
- › The EAB has participated in our Consortium Meetings to update the Project and its stakeholders on their activities and offer guidance on areas that are complicated in terms of ensuring the highest standards for data protection compliance and ethical matters. EAB members have also commented directly on the research protocols and approaches with the participant experience as the top priority.
- › Examples include:
 - › input on participant feedback about their experiences
 - › offering a broader ethical and practical view on using only minimal identifying data when needed, including the use of synthetic data for system testing purposes.
- › They have been particularly interested in the patient engagement work and have aligned more with the Patient Advisory Board, inviting its chair to attend EAB meetings and vice versa, offering a more collaborative and richer view on what they are working on in terms of patient experience.

The EAB has been delighted to work with AIDAVA and looks forward to continuing its support for AIDAVA through G2 development and evaluation of the programme.

Members

Figure 6 Ethics Advisory Board section on the AIDAVA website

2.1.2. Project management platform

To ensure smooth communication and a secure place for storing internal documents for project management, during the first project period, EURICE created an AIDAVA platform⁶ (Figure 7).

⁶ <https://aidava.eurice.eu/>

Open (2)	In Progress (0)	In Internal Review (0)	Final (5)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverable #707 D7.3 Internal progress report 2 Christa Dretter Deliverable #708 D7.6 Results Ownership List Agreement Patricia Aboen 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deliverable #706 D7.4 Internal progress report 1 Gabrijela Radic Deliverable #703 D7.1 Project Management Platform Christa Dretter Deliverable #704 D7.2 Management Guide Christa Dretter Deliverable #705 D7.5 Risk Management & Mitigation Plan Christa Dretter Milestone #709 M51 Kick-off meeting held; governance structure established Remzi Celabi

Figure 7 AIDAVA platform - monitoring deliverables and milestones status for WP7

2.1.3. Audio-visual materials

The official AIDAVA project audio-video material (see Deliverable D6.5 “Audio-visual material”⁷) is available both on the YouTube channel⁸ and on the home page of the AIDAVA website (Figure 8). The video was well accepted by a broader audience and attracted more than 1,300 viewers over an approximately one-year period.

Figure 8 AIDAVA project video in the YouTube channel (left) and on the AIDAVA website home page (right)

2.1.4. Other multipurpose materials

Another type of dissemination and communication material for broader audiences is the AIDAVA periodic communication flash (Figure 9), which is issued twice per year. The main purpose of this communication material is to provide brief, recurring updates, keeping stakeholders informed of the status, achievements, results, and next steps of the AIDAVA project. It is translated in the 3 languages of the project (Estonian, German and Dutch).

The communication flash improves transparency and builds trust. It is essentially targeted to patient consultants and to the patients across the different sites, who contributed to the G1 evaluation and are hopefully ready to support G2 assessment.

⁷ D6.5 “Audio-visual material” <https://zenodo.org/records/15434519>

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oRLB7iBDYnw>

Flash Communication / November 2024

Thanks to all the patients who helped us (and are still helping us!)

Funded by the European Union

www.aidava.eu

Figure 9 AIDAVA periodic flash - issue March 2025

2.2. Dissemination activities report

2.2.1. Scientific Publications

The AIDAVA research results were published in 10 peer-reviewed scientific publications and 6 preprints for the reported period M19-M36. Since the beginning of the AIDAVA project, the total number of peer-reviewed publications is 20 and the total number of preprints is 8 (Figure 10), which received 735 citations in Google Scholar. The full list of publications is available in Appendix 1 List of publications. Another indicator of the high quality of the scientific output is that 15 of these papers were indexed in Scopus (Figure 11), there are 10 publications indexed in PubMed Central (Figure 13) and 15 publications are indexed in Web of Science (Figure 12). These are the three collections of highly reputable scientific publications from journals and conferences. In total, 18 (out of 20 – 90%) publications are indexed in at least one of these collections, and 8 (40%) publications are indexed in all three collections. The preprints allow rapid sharing of emerging scientific research and receiving immediate attention and feedback, which allows improvement of the research results before submission for peer review publication.

Harzing's Publish or Perish (Windows GUI Edition) 8.18.5091.9307

Search terms: 101057062 from 2022 to 2025, AIDAVA, AIDAVA from 2022 to 2025

Search terms	Source	Papers	Cites	Cites/year	h	g	hI,norm	hI,annual	hA	acc10	Search date	Cache date
101057062 from 2022 to 2025, AIDAVA	Google Sch...	24	735	367.50	6	24	4	2.00	6	6	9/1/2025	9/1/2025
AIDAVA	Semantic Sc...	2	3	3.00	1	1	0	0.00	1	0	8/26/2025	8/26/2025
AIDAVA from 2022 to 2025	PubMed	2	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00	0	0	8/26/2025	8/26/2025

Citation metrics

- Publication years: 2023-2025
- Citation years: 2 (2023-2025)
- Papers: 24
- Citations: 735
- Cites/year: 367.50
- Cites/paper: 30.63
- Cites/author: 144.63
- Papers/author: 5.50
- Authors/paper: 4.67
- h-index: 6
- g-index: 24
- hI,norm: 4
- hI,annual: 2.00
- hA-index: 6
- Papers with ACC >= 1,2,5,10,20: 14,12,6,6,4

Google Scholar search

Authors: _____ Years: 2022 - 2025 Search

Publication name: _____ ISSN: _____ Search Direct

Title words: _____ Clear All

Keywords: 101057062 Revert

Maximum results: 500 Include: CITATIONS Patents Only review articles New

Cites	Per year	Rank	Authors	Title
155	155.00	4	K Lekadir, AF Frangi, AR Porras, B Glocker, C Cintas...	FUTURE-AI: international consensus guideline for trustworthy and depl
2	2.00	5	A Van Camp, E Punter, K Houbrechts...	An automated toolbox for microcalcification cluster modeling for marr
0	0.00	6	A Van Camp, HC Woodruff...	Impact of synthetic data on training a deep learning model for lesion c
2	2.00	10	Y Widaatalla, T Wolswijk, MD Khan, I Hallaj, K Mosterd...	Radiomics in dermatological optical coherence tomography (OCT): Fea
0	0.00	12	Y Zhang, Z Salahuddin, D Khan, SA Mali...	A Foundation Model Framework for Multi-View MRI Classification of Es
0	0.00	14	SA Mali, NM Rad, HC Woodruff, A Depeursinge...	Harmonizing CT scanner acquisition variability in an anthropomorphic i
3	3.00	16	PA Laurent, F André, A Bobard, D Deandreis...	Pushing the boundaries of radiotherapy-immunotherapy combinations:
0	0.00	19	I Hallaj, RIV Lieverse, CJG Oberije, LEL Hendriks...	Improving Patient Engagement in Phase 2 Clinical Trials with a Trial-spe
0	0.00	21	H Khan, HC Woodruff, DL Giraldo, L Werthen-Brabants...	Leveraging Hand-Crafted Radiomics on Multicenter FLAIR MRI for Prec
0	0.00	22	SA Mali, Z Salahuddin, D Khan, Y Zhang...	Pixels to Prognosis: Harmonized Multi-Region CT-Radiomics and Foun
0	0.00	23	D Khan, Z Salahuddin, Y Zhang, S Kuang...	Explainable Anatomy-Guided AI for Prostate MRI: Foundation Models i
1	1.00	1	A Van Camp, HC Woodruff...	Simulated image-specific microcalcification clusters and associated ma
4	4.00	3	I de Zegher, K Norak, D Steiger, H Müller...	Artificial intelligence based data curation: enabling a patient-centric Eur
11	11.00	7	A Kugic, S Schulz, M Kreuzthaler	Disambiguation of acronyms in clinical narratives with large language r
0	0.00	13	Z Salahuddin, A Ibrahim, S Kuang, Y Widaatalla...	Counterfactuals and Uncertainty-Based Explainable Paradigm for the Ai
16	16.00	15	J Gu, X Zhong, C Fang, W Lou, P Fu...	Deep learning of multimodal ultrasound: stratifying the response to ne
1	1.00	18	X Zhong, Z Salahuddin, Y Chen, HC Woodruff...	Methodological explainability evaluation of an interpretable deep learn
5	2.50	2	S Mehryar, R Celebi	Semantic Annotation of Tabular Data for Machine-to-Machine Interope
41	20.50	8	A Holzinger, A Saranti, A Angerschim, B Finzel...	Toward human-level concept learning: Pattern benchmarking for AI alg
433	216.50	9	A Holzinger, K Keiblinger, P Holub, K Zatloukal...	AI for life: Trends in artificial intelligence for biotechnology
57	28.50	11	MDI Bouyou, MRI Lekker, Y van Milik, Y Midstall...	Combining deep learning and handcrafted radiomics for classification

Figure 10 Publish and Perish query for AIDAVA GA 101057062 in Google Scholar for the period 2022-2025

Scopus

Search Sources

Advanced query

Search within Funding information Search documents * AIDAVA

OR

Search within Funding number Search documents 101057062

Save search Set search alert Add search field Reset Search

Documents Preprints Secondary documents

15 documents found

Refine search

Search within results

Filters

Year

- Article - Open access
- 1 Generating Explanations in Medical Question-Answering by Expectation Maximization Inference over Evidence
 - Sun, W., Li, M., Sileo, D., Davis, J., Moens, M.-F.
 - ACM Transactions on Computing for Healthcare, 2025, 6(2), 23
 - Show abstract View at Publisher Related documents
- 2 Radiomics in Dermatological Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT): Feature Repeatability, Reproducibility, and Integration into Diagnostic Models in a Prospective Study
 - Widaatalla, Y., Wolswijk, T., Khan, M.D., ... Woodruff, H.C., Lambin, P.
 - Cancers, 2025, 17(5), 768

Figure 11 AIDAVA publications indexed in Scopus, search by Funding number 101057062 and Funding information AIDAVA

Figure 12 AIDAVA publications indexed in Web of Science - search keyword AIDAVA

Figure 13 AIDAVA publications indexed in PubMed Central – search by Grant number 101057062 and AIDAVA

AIDAVA publication output falls in the following three categories: journal articles (63.16%), conference papers (31.58%), and review papers (5.26%). The distribution of AIDAVA publications indexed in Scopus in these three categories is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14 AIDAVA publication distributed by types: journal articles, conference papers, and reviews

The interdisciplinary nature of AIDAVA objectives and research areas defines a broader spectrum of topics that are covered by AIDAVA publications, with predominant topics: Computer science interdisciplinary, Computer Science AI, Medical informatics, Medicine, Oncology (Figure 15 and Figure 16). The more specific topic Oncology is closely related to one of the AIDAVA use cases, breast cancer.

Figure 15 Subject area of AIDAVA publications indexed in Scopus

One publication is in German (Publication 20), and all of the rest are in English. This allows to popularise the AIDAVA project objectives and results also at the local level and contributes to the development of scientific terminology in European languages other than English and to the dissemination of AIDAVA results to reach non-English-speaking audiences.

Figure 16 Distribution of AIDAVA publications per Web of Science categories

The citation overview of AIDAVA publications is another indicator for the scientific impact of the research results presented in them, achieving an h-index of 6 in Google Scholar (Figure 10) with 735 citations, Scopus (Figure 17) with 378 citations, and Web of Science with 296 citations, excluding self-citations.

Figure 17 Citation overview of AIDAVA papers indexed in Scopus

Figure 18 AIDAVA publications citations overview in Web of Science

It is worth mentioning that AIDAVA publications gained a lot of attention not only in scientific literature but also on social media. Comprehensive research metrics for scientific impact, like Altmetric⁹ and PlumX Metrics¹⁰ provide insights about publication repositories, measure awareness and interest in publications. In addition, some of the official online journal publishers provide links to Altmetric and PlumX, as well as analytics for views and downloads. For example, one of the joint publications of the AIDAVA project consortium (see publication 10, Appendix 1 List of publications) generated more than 6.6K views and 1.5K downloads (Figure 19), 2 social media posts, and 26 readers in Mendeley (Figure 20). A good example for publications with high scientific impact is publication 13 (Figure 21) – see Appendix 1 List of publications. Publication 13 not only has accumulated a high number of citations, but also attracted 785 readers in Mendeley, targeting researchers, and it was mentioned in 3 news articles and 67 Facebook social media posts, targeting a broader audience.

⁹ <https://www.altmetric.com/>

¹⁰ <https://www.elsevier.com/insights/metrics/plumx>

Figure 19 Article impact metrics from the journal website for publication 10

Figure 20 Altmetric metrics for publication 10 - geographic and demographic breakdown

Figure 21 PlumX metrics for publication 13

AIDAVA project dissemination activities comply with Open Science good practices (Figure 22), which is a step towards European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). All deliverables that are public are available in Zenodo and linked to the AIDAVA project website. AIDAVA publications have open access and can be accessed through various scientific publications repositories – the official journal/conference proceedings, indexed in Scopus, Web of Science, and one of the largest collections of full-text publications in medicine – PubMed Central. All of these are indicated in the OpenAIRE AIDAVA project website¹¹ (Figure 23), where 41 publications (scientific publications and deliverables) and 1 Data management plan are linked.

Figure 22 OpenAIRE dashboards for AIDAVA project

Figure 23 AIDAVA project in OpenAIRE

According to the categorisation of AIDAVA project publications in OpenAIRE, they also contribute to Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) (Figure 24). The majority of the AIDAVA scientific publications are related to Goal 3 “Good Health and Well Being”, there are also some publications related to Goal 10 “Reduced Inequality”, and Goal 8 “Decent Work and Economic Growth”. These are indicators for the societal and economic impact of the AIDAVA project research output.

Figure 24 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)

2.2.2. Dissemination of deliverables

The AIDAVA project deliverables play an important role in the detailed description of the AIDAVA project objectives and achievements. To contribute to Open Science, all AIDAVA public deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo (Figure 25). This ensures their sustainability – providing DOI (digital object identifier), open access, provides a platform for better visibility, direct indexing in OpenAIRE, and linkage to the Funding and Tenders portal. Since the project started, AIDAVA deliverables accumulated **1,780 views in total** and **1,385 downloads** from different users, which gives an average of **84.76 views per deliverable** and **65.95 downloads** (Figure 26). This is an indication of the high impact of AIDAVA deliverables and awareness of society about AIDAVA results. The deliverables that attracted more views/downloads are those related to use cases, global data sharing standard, and the overall AIDAVA platform solution:

- D1.4 Definition of assessment study including test scenarios & metrics, and study initiation package (192 views, 147 downloads);
- D2.1 Global Data Sharing Standard (157 views, 100 downloads);

- D1.1 Description of use cases (153 views, 129 downloads);
- D3.1 VA architecture (Application and Technical) (150 views, 110 downloads);
- D1.3 Business requirements for G1 (144 views, 90 downloads);
- D4.1 Annotation guidelines (132 views, 91 downloads).

Figure 25 AIDAVA deliverables in Zenodo

Figure 26 Dissemination report for AIDAVA deliverables in Zenodo

2.3. Communication activities report

2.3.1. Social Media Networks

Since the AIDAVA project started, several social media accounts for the project have been created:

- LinkedIn¹² (Figure 31)
- X (formerly known as Twitter)¹³ (Figure 29)
- YouTube¹⁴ (Figure 32)

Recently there were observed trends on a global level of decreased activities of users in X. Thus, it is not surprising that the number of X followers of the AIDAVA project did not increase significantly for the reported period but in fact dropped from 50 to 38, and the activity of the current followers, overall reactions and impressions are lower than the previous reported period. Despite these global trends the AIDAVA project account and partners accounts regularly posted updates about project results and events (Figure 28), including events where AIDAVA project results are presented, updates about EAB feedback, pilots with patients for AIDAVA prototype G1, among others. There is still a stable interest in AIDAVA posts with almost 1,000+ impressions (Figure 27).

AIDAVA activity on X

Figure 27 Statistics about social Media posts in X (former Twitter) from the AIDAVA project profile and some of the AIDAVA consortium partners' profiles

Figure 28 AIDAVA project social media posts in X

¹² <https://be.linkedin.com/showcase/aidava-project/>

¹³ https://twitter.com/aidava_project

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@aidavaproject>

Figure 29 AIDAVA project profile in X (former Twitter)

The most active presence of the AIDAVA project was on LinkedIn (Figure 30) with about 75 posts for the reporting period. The increase of followers of the AIDAVA project in LinkedIn is 56% in comparison to the previous reporting period M1-M18. In line with the AIDAVA project X profile, the major topics of posts were related to AIDAVA members participating in various events, highlights of AIDAVA project results and communication and networking activities, as well as presentations of AIDAVA publications at scientific conferences and workshops. AIDAVA project profile in LinkedIn (Figure 31) analytics demonstrate significant interest after the AIDAVA prototype G1 demonstration and constant interest after that, following all updates about development of the AIDAVA G2 prototype.

AIDAVA activity on LinkedIn

Figure 30 Statistics about social Media posts in LinkedIn from the AIDAVA project profile and some of the AIDAVA consortium partners' profiles

Figure 31 AIDAVA project profile in LinkedIn analytics

Another social media profile of the AIDAVA project is the YouTube channel (Figure 32) that contains training materials from AIDAVA webinars, official AIDAVA video, patient interviews about the value of AIDAVA and video about the AIDAVA objectives and solutions.

Figure 32 AIDAVA project profile on YouTube

2.3.2. News, Blogposts, Media activities

The AIDAVA website had a key role in popularising project developments and outcomes through the publication of 25 news items throughout the period about events participation, significant milestones achieved and patient engagement stories. A distinctive news item put in focus an opinion paper about the proposed solution in AIDAVA for health data interoperability (Figure 33).

Coverage by external outlets included a feature piece in *HealthcareITNews*¹⁵ about the contribution of AIDAVA to the European Health Data Spaces towards personalised medicine (Figure 34). In an article in Estonia's largest weekly newspaper *Maaleht*¹⁶ our partner NEMC introduced AIDAVA as one of the two innovative EU-funded projects with Estonian participation that help improve medical care with AI (Figure 35).

16/08/2024

AIDAVA Opinion Paper: A roadmap for health data interoperability

To solve the problem of interoperability and quality of health data, we need a structured roadmap, involving individuals as active stakeholders.

[DOWNLOAD AS PDF](#)

August 2024

Dr Isabelle de Zegher, MD, MSc,
Senior Advisor Health MyData,
Member of the Board of Directors SNOMED International,
Clinical coordinator AIDAVA.

Prof Remzi Celebi, PhD,
Assistant Professor Maastricht University Department of Advanced Computing Sciences,
Technical coordinator AIDAVA.

Figure 33 AIDAVA opinion paper: A roadmap for health data interoperability

¹⁵ <https://www.healthcareitnews.com/news/emea/aidava-harnessing-data-altruism-advance-personalised-medicine>

¹⁶ <https://maaleht.delfi.ee/artikkel/120351271/dr-tehisaru-ehk-kuidas-ai-aitab-pakkuda-inimestele-paremat-arstiabi>

Figure 34 News about AIDAVA at Healthcare IT News media channel

Figure 35 Maaleht article featuring AIDAVA

2.3.3. Events Participation

During the period M19-M36 AIDAVA project results were presented in 8 events, including scientific conferences and workshops. Two of those events were co-organised by AIDAVA consortium partners:

1. **3rd Symposium on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine and Healthcare**¹⁷ (22-23 May 2025 in Maastricht), organised by partner UM, where our Principal Investigator Dr. Michel Dumontier

¹⁷ <https://aimedicinesymposium.com/>

delivered a keynote presentation promoting the achievements of the AIDAVA project. Overall, the symposium provided insights into the latest AI innovations, real-world applications, and global success stories that are shaping the future of medicine and healthcare (Figure 36).

2. **Health Data Summit 2025** (19-20 March 2025 in Brussels),¹⁸ organised by partner i~HD (Figure 37) – This event brought together experts from diverse healthcare sectors to discuss innovative approaches and best practices to ensure the reliability of health data from collection to utilisation. Our clinical coordinator Dr. Isabelle de Zegher delivered a keynote on “Health Data Quality, What is My Return as A Citizen?” and our technical coordinator Dr. Remzi Celebi contributed to the session “Advanced Strategies and Tools for Ensuring High-Quality Data during Data Mapping” with an innovative talk, where he explained the difficulty of mapping data sources to data standards such as FHIR and SNOMED.

The image shows a speaker card for Dr. Michel Dumontier. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for HOME, ABOUT, SPEAKERS (highlighted in green), PROGRAM, and VENUE AND CONTACTS, along with a REGISTER NOW button. Below the menu is the title 'Speakers' in a large green font. On the left is a portrait of Dr. Michel Dumontier, a man with glasses wearing a dark sweater over a white collared shirt. To the right of the portrait is his name 'Michel Dumontier' in a large green font, followed by a detailed biographical text in a smaller black font.

HOME ABOUT **SPEAKERS** PROGRAM VENUE AND CONTACTS REGISTER NOW

Speakers

Michel Dumontier

Dr. Michel Dumontier is the Distinguished Professor of Data Science at Maastricht University, founder and executive director of the Institute of Data Science, co-founder of the Department of Advanced Computing Sciences, and co-founder of the influential FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Data Principles. His research focuses on computational learning and reasoning towards drug discovery and personalized medicine. He is coordinator for the REALM project to build a regulatory sandbox for (AI) medical software devices, Principal Investigator (PI) for the AIDAVA project to create an AI assistant in the curation of personal health knowledge graphs, PI for the ARPA-H CHARM project, and a PI for the iCare4CVD IHI Project. He is the editor-in-chief for the journal Data Science and is internationally recognized for his contributions in bioinformatics, biomedical informatics, and semantic technologies. His commitment to responsible discovery science and data-driven healthcare solutions positions him as a leading figure in the digital transformation of health and medicine.

Figure 36 Speaker card of Dr. Michel Dumontier for the 3rd Symposium on Artificial Intelligence in Medicine and Healthcare

¹⁸ <https://www.i-hd.eu/events/health-data-summit-25>

Figure 37 Dr. Celebi at Health Data Summit 2025

AIDAVA was represented by our clinical coordinator Dr. Isabelle de Zegher at two high-profile scientific events in the fields of digital health and data-driven innovation: Radical Health Festival Helsinki 2024¹⁹ and HIMSS Europe 2025²⁰. At the first event Dr. de Zegher presented the AIDAVA VA prototype and at HIMSS she took part in a high-level session “From Population to Personal”, highlighting the quality of data for individual patients (Figure 38).

¹⁹ <https://radicalhealthfestival.messukeskus.com/rhfh-2024/>

²⁰ <https://www.himss.org/events-overview/european-health-conference-and-exhibition/>

Figure 38 Dr. de Zegher at Radical Health Festival Helsinki and HIMSS

UM researchers presented AIDAVA achievements at two other scientific conferences that bridge AI and healthcare: European Conference on the Future of AI in HealthCare²¹ (Ai4HealthCare), 20-21 November 2024 in Copenhagen and SWAT4HCLS 2025²², 24-27 February 2025 in Barcelona (Figure 39 and Figure 40 respectively). At Ai4HealthCare UM team member Petros Kalendralis introduced the AIDAVA project to the audience by presenting the latest results of the AIDAVA prototype testing at Maastric Clinic and Maastricht University Medical Centre for breast cancer and cardiovascular disease patients. The SWAT4HCLS 2025 conference enabled our partners to engage in an open, dynamic dialogue with stakeholders from academia, industry and institutional frameworks, who all work towards the future of life sciences and semantic technologies.

²¹ <https://ai4healthcare-2024.com/>

²² <https://www.swat4ls.org/workshops/barcelona2025/>

Figure 39 AIDAVA participation in Ai4HealthCare

Figure 40 AIDAVA talk at SWAT4HCLS 2025

Another scientific event with the participation of UM PhD candidate Wenjie Liang was Vitalis 2025²³ (Figure 41). Her work on AIDAVA secured her an Award of Distinction from the Young Scientists' Forum 2024 (Figure 42).

Programpunkter Spåröversikt Biljett till Vitalis Vitalis hemsida

Konferensprogram • Conference programme

Vitalis 2025

Vitalis 2025 / Programpunkter / AIDAVA: AI based DATA curation and publishing Virtual Assistant

AIDAVA: AI based DATA curation and publishing Virtual Assistant Star passenger

Onsdag 21 maj 2025 14:00 - 14:15 Vitalis Plaza

Föreläsare: Wenjie Liang

Spår: Health data

This presentation will introduce the Horizon Europe project, AIDAVA. The project that started in September 2022 and aims to provide patients (or their delegate) with an AI-based virtual assistant that maximises automation in the integration and transformation of their health data into an interoperable, longitudinal health record. This personal record can then be used for multiple purposes: to generate patient related information such as in International Patient Summary in FHIR format or a specific risk score for the patients, or to derive population datasets for research and policymaking such as a clinical registries. The proposed solution will enable a much-needed paradigm shift in health data management, implementing a 'curate once at patient level, use many times' approach, primarily for the benefit of patients and their care providers, but also for more efficient generation of high-quality secondary datasets. The first generation of the prototype was evaluated with patients in 3 sites. While this first prototype is - as expected, suboptimal but well accepted by the patients - it demonstrates that there is true potential for automation in data curation of health data into an harmonised semantic standard, under the form of a Personal Health Knowledge Graph. The second generation of the prototype to be developed in the next 24 months will focus on the improvements in the curation tools and overall performance in data curation.

The call will focus on the following aspects

- high level project objectives and architecture with different technology components
- results of the evaluation of the first generation of the prototype and plans for the second generation
- how AIDAVA could enable interoperability of healthcare authorities and healthcare organisations as part of implementation of the EHDS

Språk
English

Ämne
Data och information

Seminarieryp
Live • på plats

Föreläsningsformat
Presentation

Föreläsningssyfte
Verktyg för implementering

Kunskapsnivå
Fördjupning

Målgrupp
Chef/Beslutsfattare
Politiker

Figure 41 AIDAVA presentation at Vitalis 2025

²³ <https://invitepeople.com/public/events/bd0a6002b4/seminars/cf7627d686>

Figure 42 Wenjie Liang's recognition for her work on AIDAVA

Partner GND presented the project from an interesting perspective, namely by illustrating UX challenges in science through the AIDAVA use case at a local Romanian event, called Sepsi Design Week (October 2024) – Figure 43.

The image is a promotional poster for an event. At the top right, the 'egnosis' logo is displayed in red and black. On the left, a yellow square contains a black stylized logo resembling 'DW'. The main text, in white and yellow, reads '11 October, 5 p.m. | former Tobacco Factory' and 'UX in science - is everything working by the book?'. Below this, a row of hashtags is listed: #User-CenteredDesign #Accessibility #InclusiveDesign #AIDAVA #DesignSystems #Consistency #Innovation. At the bottom, a black and white photograph shows four people: a man with a beard and a woman with long hair on the left, and two women on the right. A yellow banner at the very bottom identifies the speakers: 'Speakers: Zsolt B. Szabó, Aranka Ravai-Nagy (presentation), Sixtine Bokor and Tímea Török'.

Figure 43 AIDAVA presented at Sepsi Design Week

2.3.4. Networking activities and Clustering activities, collaboration with other EU-funded projects and Networking

A major highlight of the networking and clustering activities in the second phase of the project was the joint workshop of AIDAVA and RES-Q+ ontology experts at the offices of partner AVER in Freiburg (11-12 November 2024). The objective was to assess the ontologies being currently developed in both projects and how an upper-level ontology could help solve the different issues encountered and potentially align ontologies of both projects (Figure 44). This activity strengthens synergies between projects in the InToEHR cluster.

Figure 44 AIDAVA and RES-Q+ ontology workshop

A team of AIDAVA partners took part in the dAlbetes project General Assembly Meeting on 13 December 2024 to showcase the AIDAVA approach and discuss the potential of further adoption and reuse of the AIDAVA solution for other use cases such as Diabetes Mellitus (Figure 45).

A last word... Long Term perspective

dAlbetes is working with existing - heterogeneous - registries

- Maintenance requires work (and money)
- Skills of staff may vary, with potential impact on **quality of content** (different human interpretation) => difficult to detect

AIDAVA could be used to start FROM data sources to generate directly dAlbetes registries (decrease cost, increase consistency and quality)

Figure 45 Concluding slide of the AIDAVA presentation at dAlbetes GAM

ONTO lead researcher Svetla Boytcheva took the opportunity for networking with the Biotechnology and Health Cluster and the Artificial Intelligence Cluster in Bulgaria at the Spinoff Europa 2025 conference (19-20 June in Sofia). The forum brought together over 300 participants from more than 20 countries – representatives of European institutions, universities, scientific organisations, investors and technology companies, including an international selection of promising medtech companies presenting high-potential solutions with global impact (Figure 46).

Figure 46 Svetla Boytcheva engaged in networking at Spinoff Europa 2025

Another networking activity with a local impact was the introduction of the AIDAVA project, its goals and the possibilities for health data curation to the members of the Data Wisdom Network webinar on 20 March 2025 by partner NEMC.

At the policymaking level, AIDAVA contributed to three online workshops on the reuse of health data resources in the field of cancer research organised by the EC: “Landscaping data driven projects and initiatives in the cancer field – rationale and directions for better collaboration and integration”.

2.3.5. Patient communication activities

In the second phase of the project our communication strategy related to patient stakeholders aimed to engage them as our ambassadors. This was primarily realised through in-person discussions organised in collaboration with partner EHN.

The first such event was the AIDAVA and EHN-hosted patient consultants workshop in Brussels on 26 February 2025 (Figure 47). It brought together patient advocates, consultants, and project partners to explore the role of health data interoperability in improving patient experiences. The discussions covered a range of important topics, including how AIDAVA can benefit the wider patient community and patient perspectives on data quality scores. A key highlight was the session on patient advocacy strategies for engaging policymakers, led by EHN Project Officer Gregorio Sambataro.

Figure 47 AIDAVA Patient Consultants Workshop

At the EHN Annual Workshop and General Assembly in Stockholm, Sweden (June 2025) Kristof Vanfraechem, Founder and CEO, Data for Patients introduced the AIDAVA approach in his talk “Co-designing the digital future of Europe’s healthcare with patients and their frontline HCPs: AIDAVA” (Figure 48).

Figure 48 AIDAVA presentation at EHN Annual Workshop and General Assembly

In terms of communication messages, the AIDAVA Communication Committee has prepared messages tailored to different patient stakeholders to encourage them to engage with the project and contribute to the AIDAVA VA testing. The overarching narrative is that AIDAVA is here to serve YOU (the patient) and redefine the management of personal health data. Messages are created to resonate with patients staying at the healthcare site, patients in Estonia who already have access to their health data but could contribute to making it even more complete and reusable, as well as with the broader patient community. This work has been incorporated in the easily digestible format of a one-pager (Figure 49).

Figure 49 AIDAVA one-pager

A key highlight of our outreach activities targeted at patients is the video²⁴ with our patient consultant Caius Merşa published on the AIDAVA YouTube channel (Figure 50). He elicited the important message about how sharing health data helps taking better care of patients now and in the future.

AIDAVA Insights: Why Patient Involvement Matters

AIDAVA Project 6 subscribers Subscribe 0 Share Download Clip ...

Figure 50 Video with Caius Merşa

²⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=41Bod1XOui0>

3. Conclusion

The dissemination and communication efforts throughout the second phase of AIDAVA (M19-M36) have established the project as a recognizable initiative within the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and in the digital healthcare transformation space on a broader scale. The consortium has produced high-quality scientific output with multiple citations and fostered Open Science good practices. All public deliverables are also uploaded timely on the project website and in Zenodo, increasing visibility of results.

The high number of visits to the AIDAVA website has proven it to be a reliable and appealing source of information, thanks to the regular updates with new information about events and project developments as well as the addition of new sections about our high-profile expert Advisory Boards. LinkedIn posts published by the AIDAVA account have also generated a fair amount of engagement. Our clear and impactful messages to patients and scientific stakeholders have contributed to these accomplishments.

Consortium partners took part in a variety of high-profile conferences and symposia, which have positioned AIDAVA among the driving forces of health transformation (Radical Health Festival Helsinki 2025), facilitators of reliable health data (Health Data Summit 2025), and leaders in digital health and data-driven innovation (HIMSS 2025).

In conclusion, through the consortium's collaborative effort in dissemination and communication, AIDAVA can now be associated with transparency, sustainability and trust by its target stakeholders. Maintaining this profile is a key goal for our final phase, the achievements of which will be reported in D6.11 Update of Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities 2 (due M48).

4. Annexes

4.1. Appendix 1 List of publications

Table 1 Published peer-reviewed publications

	Publication
1	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sun, Wei; Li, Mingxiao; Sileo, Damien; Davis, Jesse J.; Moens, Marie Francine</p> <p>TITLE: Generating Explanations in Medical Question-Answering by Expectation Maximization Inference over Evidence</p> <p>(2025) ACM Transactions on Computing for Healthcare, 6 (2), art. no. 23,</p> <p>DOI: 10.1145/3712296</p> <p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105004401673&doi=10.1145%2F3712296&partnerID=40&md5=55fcdcae9a25524e804bc8ec2f3c1279</p> <p>https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001484840100003</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Association for Computing Machinery</p> <p>ISSN: 26911957, 26378051</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Article</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times.</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p> <p>WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
2	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Widaatalla, Yousif ; Wolswijk, Tom ; Khan, Muhammad Danial ; Halilaj, Iva ; Mosterd, Klara ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Lambin, Philippe</p> <p>TITLE: Radiomics in Dermatological Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT): Feature Repeatability, Reproducibility, and Integration into Diagnostic Models in a Prospective Study</p> <p>(2025) Cancers, 17 (5), art. no. 768.</p> <p>DOI: 10.3390/cancers17050768</p> <p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-86000601084&doi=10.3390%2Fcancers17050768&partnerID=40&md5=faabcbe97c5ddc9d00ac4d4b86347c8b</p> <p>https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001442265500001</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)</p> <p>ISSN: 20726694</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Article</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times.</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 2 times.</p> <p>WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
3	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Van Camp, Astrid ; Punter, Eva ; Houbrechts, Katrien ; Cockmartin, Lesley ; Prevos, Renate ; Marshall, Nicholas William ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Lambin, Philippe ; Bosmans, Hilde T.C.</p> <p>TITLE: An automated toolbox for microcalcification cluster modeling for mammographic imaging</p> <p>(2025) Medical Physics, 52 (2), pp. 1335 - 1349.</p> <p>DOI: 10.1002/mp.17521</p>

	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85209893647&doi=10.1002%2Fmp.17521&partnerID=40&md5=830abe3140f5d32e81b28c95a34bbea6 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001393215700001 https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11788264/</p> <p>PUBLISHER: John Wiley and Sons Ltd ISSN: 00942405, 24734209 ISBN: 9781622575909 CODEN: MPHYA PUBMED ID: 39569820 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 2 times WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
4	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lekadir, Karim ; Frangi, Alejandro F. ; Porras, Antonio Reyes ; Glocker, Ben ; Cintas, Celia ; Langlotz, Curtis P.M.D. ; Weicken, Eva ; Asselbergs, Folkert W. ; Prior, Fred W. ; Collins, Gary S. TITLE: FUTURE-AI: International consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable artificial intelligence in healthcare (2025) BMJ, art. no. e081554. DOI: 10.1136/bmj-2024-081554 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85217663528&doi=10.1136%2Fbmj-2024-081554&partnerID=40&md5=f8a8f2c0337c411e1b9528f7ce0520c6 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001427239400009</p> <p>PUBLISHER: BMJ Publishing Group ISSN: 00071447, 09598146, 17561833 CODEN: BMJOA PUBMED ID: 39909534 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: aip OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 56 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 155 times WOS CITATION: Cited 48 times</p>
5	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Laurent, Pierre Antoine ; André, Fabrice ; Bobard, Alexandre ; Deandreis, Désirée ; Demaria, Sandra ; Depil, Stéphane ; Eichmüller, Stefan B. ; Fernandez-Palomo, Cristian ; Fojier, Floris ; Galluzzi, Lorenzo TITLE: Pushing the boundaries of radiotherapy-immunotherapy combinations: highlights from the 7th immunorad conference (2025) Oncoimmunology, 14 (1), art. no. 2432726. DOI: 10.1080/2162402X.2024.2432726 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85212767581&doi=10.1080%2F2162402X.2024.2432726&partnerID=40&md5=a1142047981af85a6ece7d901d823128 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001381102400001</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Taylor and Francis Ltd.</p>

	<p>ISSN: 2162402X, 21624011 PUBMED ID: 39696783 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 3 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 3 times WOS CITATION: Cited 2 times</p>
6	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Kugic, Amila ; Schulz, Stefan ; Kreuzthaler, Markus TITLE: Disambiguation of acronyms in clinical narratives with large language models (2024) Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association, 31 (9), pp. 2040 - 2046. DOI: 10.1093/jamia/ocae157 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85201767211&doi=10.1093%2Fjamia%2Focae157&partnerID=40&md5=494dbbc06af00ef047bd8b1062a7a21e https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001253440600001</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Oxford University Press ISSN: 1527974X, 10675027 CODEN: JAMAF PUBMED ID: 38917444 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS; HYBRID GOLD OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 7 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 11 times WOS CITATION: Cited 6 times</p>
7	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Gu, Jionghui ; Zhong, Xian ; Fang, Chengyu ; Lou, Wenjing ; Fu, Peifen ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Wang, Baohua ; Jiang, Tian'an ; Lambin, Philippe TITLE: Deep Learning of Multimodal Ultrasound: Stratifying the Response to Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy in Breast Cancer Before Treatment (2024) Oncologist, 29 (2), pp. E187 - E197. DOI: 10.1093/oncolo/oyad227 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85183808180&doi=10.1093%2Foncolo%2Foyad227&partnerID=40&md5=0f5f23ae613cdd65c79f62e5d5db0a40 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001058722300001</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Oxford University Press ISSN: 10837159, 1549490X CODEN: OCOLF PUBMED ID: 37669223 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 15 times Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 16 times WOS CITATION: Cited 12 times</p>

8	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Van Camp, Astrid ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Cockmartin, Lesley ; Marshall, Nicholas William ; Bosmans, Hilde T.C. ; Lambin, Philippe</p> <p>TITLE: Simulated image-specific microcalcification clusters and associated mass enhancement to enhance training of a deep learning model for cancer detection in contrast-enhanced mammography</p> <p>(2024) Proceedings of SPIE - The International Society for Optical Engineering, 13174, art. no. 1317404.</p> <p>DOI: 10.1117/12.3026879</p> <p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195387939&doi=10.1117%2F12.3026879&partnerID=40&md5=0a1792e924d04a355758b79d306abc12</p> <p>https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001239315300003</p> <p>PUBLISHER: SPIE</p> <p>SPONSORS: Barco, Inc., Beekley Medical, Clarix Imaging, CMR Molecular Imaging, Densitas Health, et al.</p> <p>CONFERENCE NAME: 17th International Workshop on Breast Imaging, IWBI 2024</p> <p>CONFERENCE LOCATION: Chicago, IL, Rubenstein Forum on the University of Chicago Campus</p> <p>CONFERENCE CODE: 199943</p> <p>ISSN: 0277786X, 1996756X</p> <p>ISBN: 9781510692657, 9781510690561, 9781510693302, 9781510692251, 9781510692275, 9781510693081, 9781510688728, 9781510688629, 9781510692671, 9781510693326</p> <p>CODEN: PSISD</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Conference paper</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times.</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 1 times</p> <p>WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
9	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Uma, Kanimozhi ; Moens, Marie Francine</p> <p>TITLE: Unraveling Clinical Insights: A Lightweight and Interpretable Approach for Multimodal and Multilingual Knowledge Integration</p> <p>(2024) In <i>Proceedings of the First Workshop on Patient-Oriented Language Processing (CL4Health)@ LREC-COLING 2024</i>, pp. 197-203. 2024..</p> <p>PID: https://aclanthology.org/2024.cl4health-1.24.pdf</p> <p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195173847&partnerID=40&md5=a2de9db63e18c03d719457203192f15f</p> <p>PUBLISHER: European Language Resources Association (ELRA)</p> <p>CONFERENCE NAME: 1st Workshop on Patient-Oriented Language Processing, CL4Health 2024</p> <p>CONFERENCE LOCATION: Torino</p> <p>CONFERENCE CODE: 199791</p> <p>ISBN: 9782493814258</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Conference paper</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times.</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>

10	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: de Zegher, Isabelle ; Norak, Kerli ; Steiger, Dominik ; Müller, Heimo ; Kalra, Dinesh K. ; Scheenstra, Bart ; Cina, Isabella Victoria ; Shulz, Stefan ; Uma, Kanimozhi ; Kalendralis, Petros</p> <p>TITLE: Artificial intelligence based data curation: enabling a patient-centric European health data space</p> <p>(2024) <i>Frontiers in Medicine</i>, 11, art. no. 1365501.</p> <p>DOI: 10.3389/fmed.2024.1365501</p> <p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85194705386&doi=10.3389%2Ffmed.2024.1365501&partnerID=40&md5=adbd33817efa5c8e7ef5b6398e03ab24</p> <p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11133575/</p> <p>https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001233409000001</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Frontiers Media SA</p> <p>ISSN: 2296858X</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Article</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 4 times.</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 4 times.</p> <p>WOS CITATION: Cited 2 times</p>
11	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Holzinger, Andreas T. ; Saranti, Anna ; Angerschmid, Alessa ; Finzel, Bettina ; Schmid, Ute ; Mueller, Heimo</p> <p>TITLE: Toward human-level concept learning: Pattern benchmarking for AI algorithms</p> <p>(2023) <i>Patterns</i>, 4 (8), art. no. 100788.</p> <p>DOI: 10.1016/j.patter.2023.100788</p> <p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85167997340&doi=10.1016%2Fj.patter.2023.100788&partnerID=40&md5=6772763735a640ff6f9e3ffde7fc6079</p> <p>https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001059101300001</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Cell Press</p> <p>ISSN: 26663899</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Review</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 26 times.</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 41 times</p> <p>WOS CITATION: Cited 22 times</p>
12	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Beuque, Manon P.L. ; Lobbes, Marc B.I. ; van Wijk, Yvonka ; Widaatalla, Yousif ; Primakov, Sergey P. ; Majer, Michael ; Balleyguier, Corinne S. ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Lambin, Philippe</p> <p>TITLE: Combining Deep Learning and Handcrafted Radiomics for Classification of Suspicious Lesions on Contrast-enhanced Mammograms</p> <p>(2023) <i>Radiology</i>, 307 (5), art. no. e221843.</p> <p>DOI: 10.1148/radiol.221843</p> <p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163922659&doi=10.1148%2Fradiol.221843&partnerID=40&md5=11f33bde2ceb494dbac07a2e16d328a0</p> <p>https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001061457800008</p> <p>https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37338353/</p>

	<p>PUBLISHER: Radiological Society of North America Inc. ISSN: 00338419, 15271315 CODEN: RADLA PUBMED ID: 37338353 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 44 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 57 times WOS CITATION: Cited 38 times.</p>
13	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Holzinger, Andreas T. ; Keiblinger, Katharina Maria ; Holub, Petr ; Zatloukal, Kurt ; Müller, Heimo TITLE: AI for life: Trends in artificial intelligence for biotechnology (2023) New Biotechnology, 74, pp. 16 - 24. DOI: 10.1016/j.nbt.2023.02.001 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85147548778&doi=10.1016%2Fj.nbt.2023.02.001&partnerID=40&md5=af0c0f47eb4e7a94387ab23fad2ea5ca https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000936300300001 https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36754147/</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Elsevier B.V. ISSN: 18764347, 18716784 PUBMED ID: 36754147 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 253 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 433 times WOS CITATION: Cited 172 times</p>
14	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mehryar, Shervin ; Çelebi, Remzi TITLE: Semantic Annotation of Tabular Data for Machine-to-Machine Interoperability via Neuro-Symbolic Anchoring (2023) CEUR Workshop Proceedings, 3557, pp. 61 - 71. PID: https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3557/paper5.pdf https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85179125925&partnerID=40&md5=fe8923a43ba479c98737d70047faad46</p> <p>PUBLISHER: CEUR-WS CONFERENCE NAME: 2023 Semantic Web Challenge on Tabular Data to Knowledge Graph Matching, SemTab 2023 CONFERENCE LOCATION: Athens CONFERENCE CODE: 194580 ISSN: 16130073 ISBN: 9789666544899, 9788073780029, 9788024810256, 9789986342748, 9788073781712, 9782954494807, 9788024823911, 9789562361989, 8024810255, 807378002X DOCUMENT TYPE: Conference paper PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 1 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 5 times.</p>

15	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Schulz, Stefan ; Del-Pinto, Warren ; Han, Lifeng ; Kreuzthaler, Markus ; Aghaei, Sareh ; Nenadic, Goran</p> <p>TITLE: Towards principles of ontology-based annotation of clinical narratives (2023) CEUR Workshop Proceedings, 3603, pp. 36 - 47.</p> <p>PID: https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3603/icbo2023_proceedings.pdf#page=51 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85178585442&partnerID=40&md5=00f37d20b44ee07a2ff64d86ac809e06</p> <p>PUBLISHER: CEUR-WS</p> <p>SPONSORS: Alma Sirio-Libanos</p> <p>CONFERENCE NAME: 14th International Conference on Biomedical Ontologies, ICBO 2023</p> <p>CONFERENCE LOCATION: Brasilia</p> <p>CONFERENCE CODE: 196075</p> <p>ISSN: 16130073</p> <p>ISBN: 9789666544899, 9788073780029, 9788024810256, 9789986342748, 9788073781712, 9782954494807, 9788024823911, 9789562361989, 8024810255, 807378002X</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Conference paper</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times.</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 4 times</p>
16	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mali, Shruti Atul, Nastaran Mohammadian Rad, Henry C. Woodruff, Adrien Depeursinge, Vincent Andrearczyk, and Philippe Lambin</p> <p>TITLE: Harmonizing CT scanner acquisition variability in an anthropomorphic phantom: A comparative study of image-level and feature-level harmonization using GAN, ComBat, and their combination (2025) <i>PloS one</i> 20, no. 5: e0322365</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0322365 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001488720800048</p> <p>PUBLISHER: <i>PloS one</i></p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Article</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p> <p>WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
17	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Van Camp, Astrid, Henry C. Woodruff, Lesley Cockmartin, Marc Lobbes, Michael Majer, Corinne Balleyguier, Nicholas W. Marshall, Hilde Bosmans, and Philippe Lambin</p> <p>TITLE: Impact of synthetic data on training a deep learning model for lesion detection and classification in contrast-enhanced mammography (2025) <i>Journal of Medical Imaging</i> 12, no. S2: S22006-S22006.</p> <p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JMI.12.S2.S22006</p> <p>PUBLISHER: SPIE</p> <p>ISSN: 2329-4302</p> <p>DOCUMENT TYPE: Article</p> <p>PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p> <p>OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
18	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Uma, Kanimozhi, Sumam Francis, and Marie-Francine Moens</p>

	<p>TITLE: Masking language model mechanism with event-driven knowledge graphs for temporal relations extraction from clinical narratives (2023) <i>Complex Networks & Their Applications XII. COMPLEX NETWORKS 2023. Studies in Computational Intelligence</i>, vol 1141. Springer, Cham, (pp. 162-174). DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53468-3_14 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001264435300014</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Springer, Cham CONFERENCE NAME: <i>International Conference on Complex Networks and Their Applications, COMPLEX NETWORKS 2023</i> CONFERENCE LOCATION: Menton, France ISBN: 978-3-031-53467-6 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 1 times WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
19	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Uma, Kanimozhi, Sumam Francis, Wei Sun, and Marie-Francine Moens TITLE: Towards Explainability in Automated Medical Code Prediction from Clinical Records <i>Intelligent Systems and Applications.</i> (2023) <i>IntelliSys 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems</i>, vol 825. Springer, Cham (pp. 593-637). DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-47718-8_40 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001261694800040</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Springer, Cham CONFERENCE NAME: <i>Intelligent Systems and Applications, (IntelliSys 2023)</i> CONFERENCE LOCATION: Amsterdam ISBN: 978-3-031-47717-1 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 1 times WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
20	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Philipp Daumke, Christian Haverkamp, Simone Heckmann, Marcus Kuper, Annett Müller, Frank Oemig, Uta Ripperger, Stefan Sabutsch, André Sander & Stefan Schulz TITLE: Kommunikationsfähigkeit und Interoperabilität von Gesundheitsdaten in einem vernetzten Gesundheitssystem. (2024) <i>Health Data Management</i>, pp 457–496 DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-43236-2_41</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Health Data Management DOCUMENT TYPE: Chapter in a Book PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p>

Table 2 Published Preprints

	Publication
1	Zhang, Yumeng, Zohaib Salahuddin, Danial Khan, Shruti Atul Mali, Henry C. Woodruff, Sina Amirrajab, Eduardo Ibor-Crespo, Ana Jimenez-Pastor, Luis Marti-Bonmati, and Philippe Lambin. "A Foundation Model Framework for Multi-View MRI Classification of Extramural Vascular Invasion and Mesorectal Fascia Invasion in Rectal Cancer." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.18058</i> (2025). https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.18058
2	Salahuddin, Zohaib, Abdalla Ibrahim, Sheng Kuang, Yousif Widaatalla, Razvan L. Miclea, Oliver Morin, Spencer Behr et al. "Counterfactuals and Uncertainty-Based Explainable Paradigm for the Automated Detection and Segmentation of Renal Cysts in Computed Tomography Images: A Multi-Center Study." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.03789</i> (2024). https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.03789
3	Khan, Danial, Zohaib Salahuddin, Yumeng Zhang, Sheng Kuang, Shruti Atul Mali, Henry C. Woodruff, Sina Amirrajab et al. "Explainable Anatomy-Guided AI for Prostate MRI: Foundation Models and In Silico Clinical Trials for Virtual Biopsy-based Risk Assessment." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.17971</i> (2025). https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.17971
4	Zhong, Xian, Zohaib Salahuddin, Yi Chen, Henry C. Woodruff, Haiyi Long, Jianyun Peng, Nuwan Udawatte et al. "Methodological explainability evaluation of an interpretable deep learning model for post-hepatectomy liver failure prediction incorporating counterfactual explanations and layerwise relevance propagation: a prospective In silico trial." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.03771</i> (2024). https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.03771
5	Mali, Shruti Atul, Zohaib Salahuddin, Danial Khan, Yumeng Zhang, Henry C. Woodruff, Eduardo Ibor-Crespo, Ana Jimenez-Pastor, Luis Marti-Bonmati, and Philippe Lambin. "Pixels to Prognosis: Harmonized Multi-Region CT-Radiomics and Foundation-Model Signatures Across Multicentre NSCLC Data." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.17893</i> (2025). https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.17893
6	Khan, Hamza, Henry C. Woodruff, Diana L. Giraldo, Lorin Werthen-Brabants, Shruti Atul Mali, Sina Amirrajab, Edward De Brouwer et al. "Leveraging Hand-Crafted Radiomics on Multicenter FLAIR MRI for Predicting Disability Progression in People with Multiple Sclerosis." <i>medRxiv</i> (2025): 2025-01. https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2025.01.23.25320971.abstract
7	Halilaj, Iva, Relinde IY Lieverse, Cary JG Oberije, Lizza EL Hendriks, Charlotte Billiet, Ines Joye, Brice van Eeckhout, Anke Wind, Anshu Ankolekar, and Philippe Lambin. "Improving Patient Engagement in Phase 2 Clinical Trials with a Trial-specific Patient Decision Aid (tPDA): A Development and Usability Study." <i>medRxiv</i> (2025): 2025-02. https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2025.02.25.25322591.abstract
8	Kuang, Sheng, Lesley Schuitmaker, Min Wu, Zohaib Salahuddin, Alexander van der Wiel, Jella van de Laak, Natasja Lieuwes et al. "Predicting Homologous Recombination Deficiency and Treatment Responses Using a Computed Tomography-Based Foundation Model: A Preclinical Study." <i>Available at SSRN 5381282</i> . https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5381282

4.2. Appendix 2 List of some communication and dissemination activities

Table 3 Highlights of some AIDAVA communication and dissemination activities in M19-M36

	Type	Activity
1.	Conferences	Health Data Summit 2025
2.	Conferences	Symposium Artificial Intelligence in Medicine and Healthcare (https://aimedicinesymposium.com/)
3.	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Participation in three online workshops on the re-use of health data resources in the field of cancer research organised by the EC
4.	Clustering activities	AIDAVA and RES-Q+ ontology expert meeting (Nov 2024)
5.	Conferences	European Conference on the Future of AI in HealthCare (Ai4HealthCare)
6.	Meetings	Patient Consultants Face-to-Face Workshop in Brussels (26 Feb 2025)
7.	Conferences	SWAT4HCLS 2025: Bridging Life Sciences and Technology (24-27 Feb 2025)
8.	Conferences	HIMSS Europe in Paris from 10-12 June 2025
9.	Conferences	EHN Annual Workshop and General Assembly in Stockholm, Sweden (June 2025)
10.	Other	Isabelle participating in a Sitra event
11.	Conferences	Vitalis 2025
12.	Other	UX in science - AIDAVA use case on Sepsi Design Week
13.	Conferences	BEHEALTH 2025 International Event in Healthcare
14.	Conferences	Digital Seklerland International Conference
15.	Other	Newspaper article in "Maaleht", 23.01.25
16.	Other	Presentation at the Data Wisdom Network Webinar, 20.03.25
17.	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	AIDAVA project presented in GA meeting of DIABETES project, Dec 2024